

Towards Synalgebraic Photonic Quantum Computing

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Abstract—This article introduces a novel algebraic-logical formalism, called synalgebra, for describing, simulating, and reasoning about photonic quantum circuits. Existing approaches are typically limited to either descriptive languages or circuit simulators. In contrast, synalgebra employs the new concept of intergraphs as a core data structure for equational reasoning about photonic circuit architectures. Specifically, the article presents preliminary simulations of the variational quantum eigensolver (VQE) algorithm for up to 100 qubits, demonstrating how synalgebra can support higher-level abstractions of VQE as well as hardware optimization of photonic waveguides.

Index Terms—Photonic Quantum Computing, Machine Reasoning, Synalgebra

I. A KANTIAN-PEIRCEAN PERSPECTIVE ABOUT PHOTONIC QUANTUM COMPUTING

In general, the classical description and simulation of quantum circuits play a crucial role in validating quantum processors, benchmarking near-term devices, and understanding the complexity of quantum advantage demonstrations. In particular, useful photonic systems are expected to operate in high-dimensional Hilbert spaces [1]. To address this, researchers have explored tensor networks [2], mainly, but also many sampling-based techniques that trade accuracy for computational efficiency [4].

In the context of photonic simulators, the first to get traction was the *Strawberry Fields*, developed by the Xanadu’s team in 2019 [13]. Strawberry Fields was based on an API for a quantum programming language named *Blackbird* and run on Python libraries for machine learning. More recently, Kolarovszki et al. [21] designed a new simulator called *Picasso* that has a Python interface language similar to *Blackbird*, but allows modulation of the code and direct call to high-performance libraries from C/C++.

While these *simulational approaches* have enabled simulations of quantum circuits involving hundreds of qubits, an achievement worth noting, further scalability is hindered by the persistent curse of dimensionality inherent to linear algebraic representations. A tensor network, for example, is

a symbolic layer atop multilinear matrix theory, often relying on Singular Value Decomposition. Besides, the photonic simulators are wrappers of functions implemented in photonic algorithms, with no clear mathematical model of computing underlying them.

From a *descriptive perspective*, as far as we know, one of the first - if not the first - language to describe quantum photonic circuits was presented in 2012 by Tezak, Niederberger, Pavlichin, Sarma and Mabuchi in [14]. They presented a restrict, but useful, extension of the standard VHSIC hardware description language (VHDL) to photonic circuits, named *QHDL*. Recently, to overcome the expressiveness limitations of traditional perspectives like *QHDL*, some works have also explored the use of categorical models as languages to describe photonic quantum circuits, with less emphasis on simulation.

In [5], a graphical language for reasoning about linear optical quantum circuits with vacuum state auxiliary inputs was introduced. The axiomatic of the language was proven to be sound and complete with respect to equations governing photonic circuits. In [9], a functor from the ZX calculus to linear optical circuits is defined. This approach provides a compositional theory of quantum linear optics, enabling reasoning about events involving multiple photons, such as those required for linear-optical and fusion-based quantum computing.

In spite of significant advancements, none of the previous languages presents a framework to simulate computations based on an effective model of photonic computing. These languages indeed describe models of photonic computations, but they allow restricted simulations capabilities. Moreover, they usually require extra, hard, work to represent actual photonic devices symbolically.

From our standpoint, the trouble with the descriptive and simulational approaches is that they put an excessive emphasis on the *representation* of photonic circuits. While in practice, there are many challenges related to the *implementation* of algorithms in photonic devices. Not only software compilation, but also synthesis and analysis of the errors. We need an *integrative approach* between representation and implementation, specifically designed for photonic processes. The aim of the

present article is to outline a proposal in that direction.

In the 18th century, Kant [11] studied the relationship between our abstract concepts and our concrete intuitions as the interaction between noumenon and phenomenon. He argued that there must be a mediation between noumenon and phenomenon, which he termed *schemas*. For Kant, schemas are the means by which reason enables the interaction between the generality of concepts in the mind and the specificities of intuitions derived from experience. Later, Peirce [17] sought to develop this Kantian perspective through diagrams for reasoning, which he termed the *logic of relatives*. We sustain that today's challenges in understanding the relationship between software and hardware in quantum computing can be fruitfully approached through this philosophical lens. Figure I below illustrates our reframing of Kant and Peirce's ideas in the context of software-hardware relations.

Kantian-Peircean Perspective (Fig. I)

From our Kantian-Peircean perspective, the integration of photonic circuit representations with the implementation of algorithms within them is achieved through a data structure called *intergraph*. This novel concept enables reasoning across multiple levels of abstraction and concretion in quantum circuit descriptions, representing circuit components with symbolic forms that preserve the logical structure of the hardware device's workflow.

Intergraphs can be manipulated using rules from an algebraic system known as *synalgebra* (short name for *synthetic algebra*). As a result, simulations of photonic quantum circuits can be executed through synalgebraic identity rules and approximated using synalgebraic similarity rules that track computations; a feature that no other framework has intrinsically. In particular, we present preliminary simulations of the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) algorithm for circuits with up to 100 qubits, demonstrating how synalgebra supports high-level abstractions of VQE while also offering insights into concrete photonic waveguide hardware optimization.

II. AN ALGEBRA OF INTERGRAPHS CALLED SYNALGEBRA

Synalgebra is a theory for equational reasoning over levels of abstractions and concretions called *intergraphs*. An *intergraph* is a graph structure with levels that may have edges within and across other levels of different orders. An intergraph has an operation \triangleright that represents a *link* between two levels and an operation $:$ that represents *instanciation*, i.e., $a : b$ is true when a is a level inside b . The *nodes* of an intergraph are levels that have no other levels inside them. The order of a node is 0. If $a : b$ and a has the greatest order n among the levels in b , then the order of b is $n+1$. Additionally, intergraphs

have an operation $a \Delta b$ called *junction*, which represents a blend of the conjunction and disjunction; a mix between “and” and “or”. For example, an intergraph in which a is linked to b and c but also b or c are linked to d can be represented as

Junction intergraph (Fig. II)

The formula representing the intergraph in Fig. II is this

$$(a \triangleright (b \Delta c)) \triangleright d$$

Parentheses between junctions and links are not associative. For example, the meaning of the formula

$$a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d)$$

is the following intergraph

New junction intergraph (Fig. III)

The intergraphs of $(a \triangleright (b \Delta c)) \triangleright d$ and $a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d)$ are different because they have different *initial nodes*. To activate a flow of information in Fig. II, we need just the node a , but Fig. III requires a and $b \Delta c$. Synalgebra internalizes this with an operation of *application* \cdot . Thus, we have the following

$$\begin{aligned} ((a \triangleright (b \Delta c)) \triangleright d) \cdot a &= (a \triangleright (b \Delta c)) \cdot a \triangleright d \\ &= ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d) \cdot (b \Delta c) \\ &= d \\ &= (a \triangleright d) \cdot a \\ &= (a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d)) \cdot (b \Delta c) \\ &= a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \cdot a \triangleright d) \cdot (b \Delta c) \\ &= (a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \cdot a \triangleright d)) \cdot (b \Delta c) \\ &= (a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d)) \cdot a \cdot (b \Delta c) \\ &= (a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d)) \cdot (a \cdot (b \Delta c)) \end{aligned}$$

Although the intergraphs in Fig. II and Fig. III are different, they are *similar*. First, the nodes of one are the nodes of the other and, second, the initial and terminal nodes of one are the initial and terminal nodes of the other as well. Hence, intergraphs have two relations $=$ and \simeq that represent *identity* and *similarity*. In this notation, we can express that $(a \triangleright (b \Delta c)) \triangleright d \neq a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d)$ but $(a \triangleright (b \Delta c)) \triangleright d \simeq a \triangleright ((b \Delta c) \triangleright d)$.

In order to calculate identities and similarities among levels in intergraphs, synalgebra has rules of the form

$$[\Upsilon \vdash \Lambda] =_{\alpha_R} [\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta]$$

$$[\Upsilon \vdash \Lambda] =_{\alpha_L} [\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta]$$

where a *right rule* α_R indicates what happens ($Y \vdash \Lambda$) when α is true (right side of \vdash) and a *left rule* α_L indicates what happens ($Y \vdash \Lambda$) when α is false (left side of \vdash). In the rules above, the symbol Γ represent a list of *assumptions* and Δ a list of *consequences*. The symbol “ \vdash ” marks the difference between assumptions and consequences. This distinction is remanescant of Gentzen sequent calculus [15].

Synalgebra has left and right rules for identities and similarities, which provide rigorous foundations for the kind of equational reasoning illustrated above about Fig. II and Fig. III. To explain all the details is beyond the scope of the present paper, because we intend to show how to handle photonic quantum circuits. The interested reader, can look at our work [7] for a presentation of synalgebra in the context of propositional logic.

For the time being, it is sufficient to keep in mind that synalgebra is a reformulation of Shallon’s graph algebra [19], in which we interpret $a \triangleright b$ as “ b is a target of a .” It also incorporates ideas from the *multilayer networks* introduced by De Domenico et al. in [10]. Nonetheless, its motivation is an early work of us about logical modelling of quantum computational problems [6]. We identified that quantum computations require a mathematical representation of the flow of information quite different from the usual ones in algebraic logic. After many years of thoughts, studies, try and error, we discovered that a blend of ideas associated to Kant and Peirce could be promising for quantum computing. That blend is the notion of integraph and its synthetic algebra of identities and similarities.

Indeed, from a synalgebraic point of view, the fundamental *representation problem* of quantum computing is the formalization of quantum states and operations with the multi-linear algebra of matrices. This inherently demands *a priori* exponential resources to simulate quantum states and operations. For example, if we have two qubits in the $|0\rangle$ state and apply a simple Pauli NOT operation to them, their associated matrices are as follows:

$$|00\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ 0 & \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$NOT \otimes NOT = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

In this way, a quantum system with n qubits is represented by vectors containing 2^n numbers, while quantum operations acting on them are represented by $2^n \times 2^n$ matrices. To overcome that problem, synalgebra proposes to represent quantum processes with symbolic rules. It is not a replacement for the linear algebraic approach, but a complement that allows us to efficiently handle quantum systems. For instance, how can we

readily verify the truth value of the following equation?

$$NOT \otimes \dots \otimes NOT |0\rangle \dots |0\rangle = |1\rangle \dots |1\rangle$$

(Each NOT and $|0\rangle$ is grouped under a bracket labeled "1000 times")

No $2^{1000} \times 2^{1000}$ matrix is required to calculate that. We just need to leverage that $NOT \otimes NOT |0\rangle |0\rangle = NOT |0\rangle \otimes NOT |0\rangle$ and $NOT |0\rangle = |1\rangle$, and use mathematical induction. In essence, we engage in a form of *quantum reasoning* to obtain the outputs of quantum computations. Thus, synalgebra has right rules for quantum operations like *NOT*, namely,

$$[\Gamma \vdash |0\rangle \triangleright NOT, \Delta] =_{NOT_R} [\Gamma \vdash |1\rangle, \Delta]$$

$$[\Gamma \vdash |1\rangle \triangleright NOT, \Delta] =_{NOT_R} [\Gamma \vdash |0\rangle, \Delta]$$

The quantum operators are assumed to be linear. Thus, it is sufficient to define their actions on the basis of computation – the qubits $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ in the illustrated example. Of course, there are left rules for *NOT* too and, similarly, for all quantum gates and measurements.

Aside to the representation problem, there is the *calculation problem* of computing with symbols for quantum processes. Even in the case we have an efficient form of representing quantum systems, we may not be able to compute the relevant processes. Unless, of course, you believe that quantum computational classes are equal to the deterministic polynomial class P – which is not the general assumption in the whole quantum science and technology. For instance, consider the basic equation below, where H is the Hadarmard gate and \bar{k} is a list of n binary digits:

$$H \dots H |0\rangle \dots |0\rangle = \underbrace{|0\dots 0\rangle}_{n \text{ times}} + \underbrace{|0\dots 1\rangle}_{n \text{ times}} + \dots + \underbrace{|1\dots 1\rangle}_{n \text{ digits}} = \sum_{k=0}^{2^n-1} |\bar{k}\rangle$$

Such an equation contains an exponential number of terms and appears in almost every quantum algorithm that operates on numerical data – for example, Shor’s algorithm. We cannot expect to compute this type of equation for large numbers of qubits, even if we can efficiently represent quantum systems. Some form of approximation is required. Synalgebra proposes a method for efficiently approximating quantum computations by leveraging the qualitative distinction between identities = and similarities \simeq . In doing so, we can *perfectly track the structure of quantum computations* and, *a posteriori*, perform *quantitative statistical analyses* of the approximations made.

To understand the concept of *perfect track of computations*, appreciate the equational reasoning below, where H is the Hadamard gate, C^{NOT} the controlled NOT, I is the identity, \otimes the tensor product and \oplus the vector sum:

$$\begin{aligned} [\vdash C^{NOT} \circ (H \otimes I \circ |00\rangle)] &=_{\circ_R} [\vdash C^{NOT} \circ (H \circ |0\rangle \otimes I \circ |0\rangle)] \\ &=_{H_R, I_R} [\vdash C^{NOT} \circ \frac{|00\rangle \oplus |10\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}] \\ &\simeq_{C_R^{NOT}} [\vdash \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |11\rangle] \end{aligned}$$

In the last line, we lost full identity, because a similarity rule of the C^{NOT} was applied. This is the kind of *perfect track* of computations that synalgebra enable us to perform, and which is crucial to simulate quantum computations. None of the previous descriptive or simulational approaches allows computational perfect track as an intrinsic feature of the formalism. To do that, the distinction between identities and similarities is essential and, differently from our toy example above, in descriptions and simulations of real quantum hardware, computational perfect track is not an option. This leads us to the last problem.

Real quantum circuits and, the photonic ones in particular, have many different complex components subject to noise. Below it is displayed a photonic quantum circuit where the light sources, optical processing and single-photon detectors are exhibited. How can we handle such type of complex systems in a unique mathematical framework? More precisely, how can we implement – i.e. compile, analyze and synthesize – an ideal quantum algorithm into the best configuration of the real hardware that we have?

Fig. 1. Typical photonic circuit

Let us analyze how measurements work in gate circuits, for they already exemplify the complexity of quantum operations at a theoretical level - things get much worst in practice!

From a logical perspective, quantum measurements are composite operations because they involve both state generations and probability assignments. For example, if we apply the measurement projector $|1\rangle\langle 1|$ to the state $1/\sqrt{3}|0\rangle + 2/\sqrt{6}|1\rangle$, we obtain the state $|1\rangle$ with the probability $(2/\sqrt{6}) \cdot (2/\sqrt{6})^* = 2/3$, determined by Born's rule. Visually:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |1\rangle\langle 1| &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \star_1 \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}|0\rangle + \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}}|1\rangle \\
 &\quad \downarrow \\
 |1\rangle \star_2 \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}} &\cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{6}}^* = \frac{2}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the star operation \star_1 above is a relationship between a matrix like $|1\rangle\langle 1|$ and a vector like $1/\sqrt{3}|0\rangle + 2/\sqrt{6}|1\rangle$. Of course, \star_1 is the matrix multiplication \circ . Nevertheless, \star_2 is a relationship between a vector like $|1\rangle$ and a scalar that represents a probability like $(2/\sqrt{6}) \cdot (2/\sqrt{6})^*$. Hence, \star_2 must meet a vector and a probability, it is a logically complex

operation. How can we represent and implement this kind of complex operation?

One possible approach is to formalize \star_2 as indexing of states with probabilities: $|a\rangle^p$ denotes that the state $|a\rangle$ occurs with probability p . Similarly, synalgebra can also handle this kind of indexing – not only with scalars –, to represent different sorts of information such as errors, choices, paths, etc, because intergraphs are multilevel data structures. We can adapt the intergraphs to the particular instances of physical structures to be described. That is to say, the notion of intergraph is even more flexible and expressive than the notion of *category* used in mathematics [12]. Moreover, synalgebra provides rules to actually calculate over intergraphs. Thus, large-scale simulations are possible due to its intrinsic distinction between identities and similarities.

Synalgebra is a subject in itself, and so something for further works. Hopefully, the outline presented here is enough to grasp the main idea for us to look at photonic quantum circuits.

III. SYNALGEBRAIC PHOTONIC OPERATIONS

In the previous section, we indicated how to represent, calculate and implement quantum systems in general. Now, we will show a synalgebraic approach to photonic quantum circuits. We use the following symbolic notation:

- $| \rangle$ is the vacuum state;
- $|v\rangle_s$ for $v, s \in \{0, 1\}$ is a photon basis with polarization v in the spatial mode s ;
- \square_{ij}^t is the beam splitter with angle $t\pi$ at cell i, j ;
- \diamond_{ij}^t is the phase shifter at cell i, j ;
- \otimes_{ij}^t is wave plate with angle $t\pi$ at the cell i, j ;
- \star_{ij}^v is the polarizer in the v direction at cell i, j ;
- \triangle_{ij}^s is the detector for spatial mode s at cell i, j ;
- \square_{ij} is the polarizing (beam) splitter at cell i, j .

These symbols are interpreted in an intergraph \mathcal{A} in such way that the meaning $\mathcal{A}(\xi)$ for the symbol ξ in \mathcal{A} is defined according to the following:

- $\mathcal{A}(\square_{ij}^t) = |v\rangle_s \mapsto \cos \theta |v\rangle_s + i \sin \theta |v\rangle_{1-s}$
- $\mathcal{A}(\diamond_{ij}^t) = |v\rangle_s \mapsto e^{i\theta} |v\rangle_s$
- $\mathcal{A}(\otimes_{ij}^t) = \begin{cases} |1\rangle_s \mapsto \cos t\pi |1\rangle_s + i \sin t\pi |0\rangle_s \\ |0\rangle_s \mapsto \cos t\pi |0\rangle_s + i \sin t\pi |1\rangle_s \end{cases}$
- $\mathcal{A}(\star^v) = \begin{cases} |v\rangle_s \mapsto |v\rangle_s \\ |1-v\rangle_s \mapsto | \rangle \end{cases}$
- $\mathcal{A}(\triangle^s) = a |v\rangle_s \mapsto (|a|^2)_s$
- $\mathcal{A}(\square) = \begin{cases} |1\rangle_s \mapsto |1\rangle_s \\ |0\rangle_s \mapsto |0\rangle_{1-s} \end{cases}$

We do not have space here to explain the details of the definitions above, but they are intended to represent the mathematical definitions of the respective photonic devices (Cf. [16]). In this way, the meaning of the operations are translated to intergraphs that describe photonic circuits. Below it is displayed an example of a circuit intergraph:

Example of photonic intergraph circuit (Fig. IV)

To keep the presentation clear, there are some special visual features displayed in a circuit intergraph. Notably, the operations have different colors to help in the visualization, the indexes are omitted, and the arrows of the links are not displayed. Aside, the shapes are a little different (sources are isosceles triangles and detectors are trapezoids).

However, some colors express conventions. By stipulation, white triangles represent the horizontal polarization $|0\rangle_s$ and the orange ones represent the vertical $|1\rangle_s$. Similarly, white trapezoids are detectors of the 0 spacial mode $|v\rangle_0$ and oranges detect the 1 spacial mode $|v\rangle_1$. The same holds for polarizers: white are in horizontal direction $|0\rangle_s$ and orange in the vertical direction $|1\rangle_s$. We also use, in some occasions, gray detectors to block the photons. There are also *dashed links* between the input sources and the output detectors. The circuit above has two inputs and two outputs, but two photons are used to represent one input in the first row, whereas two detectors are used to represent one output in the second one. These dashed links represent how input and outputs are encoded and decoded respectively.

With these conventions, we encode *inputs in the polarization* and the *outputs in the spacial mode* of the photons. Such a kind of coding is similar to that used in [3], with the difference that we use such a codification for the whole circuit, and not just for controlled operations. Since codification in polarization and spacial mode are equivalent, our convention implies no loss of generality. As an abuse of notation, we write $|0\rangle_{ij}^t$ and $|1\rangle_{ij}^t$, or just $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, to denote the horizontal and vertical polarizations, respectively, to increase readability.

An interesting consequence of the flexibility of synalgebra is the possibility to define different conventions about input and output relations; as we did above. This implies that we can distinguish between photonic circuits that are consistent from those that are not. For instance, if we change the polarization of the filter in the circuit above (Fig. IV), we obtain a circuit whose output is the vacuum state $|\rangle$ for the input $|00\rangle$, i.e., the following circuit is inconsistent:

Example of inconsistent photonic intergraph circuit

Such a phenomenon of consistency in photonic quantum circuits is new, we guess. In a synalgebraic framework, we can formulate different layouts of representation of inputs

and outputs and explore their consistency. In future work, we intend to explore this more carefully.

Another characteristic of synalgebra is that it allows to represent linear optical circuits as logical formulas. For instance, the formula that express the consistent circuit in Fig. IV above is this:

$$|v\rangle_{00}^0 \triangleright \square_{01}^{\frac{1}{4}} \triangleright \diamond_{02}^{\frac{1}{3}} \triangleright \star_{03}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 \otimes |u\rangle_{10}^1 \triangleright \square_{11}^{\frac{1}{2}} \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0 \otimes |w\rangle_{20}^0 \triangleright \star_{21}^1 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1 \Delta (|v\rangle_{00}^0 \Delta |u\rangle_{10}^1 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 \Delta (|w\rangle_{20}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0 \Delta \triangle_{22}^1))$$

The notation is humanly hard to read, but we display it anyway for the sake of illustration. The explanation of the translation requires a work in itself too. What we want to emphasize is this: we can take a logical formula of a photonic circuit and simulate computations with synalgebra. For example, the following equational reasoning represents a computation C for the input qubit $|0, 0\rangle$:

$$\begin{aligned} C &= [|0\rangle_{00}^0 \triangleright \square_{01}^{\frac{1}{4}} \triangleright \diamond_{02}^{\frac{1}{3}} \triangleright \star_{03}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 \otimes |0\rangle_{10}^1 \triangleright \square_{11}^{\frac{1}{2}} \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0 \otimes |0\rangle_{20}^0 \triangleright \star_{21}^1 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1] \\ &= [|0\rangle_{00}^0 \triangleright \square_{01}^{\frac{1}{4}} \triangleright \diamond_{02}^{\frac{1}{3}} \triangleright \star_{03}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 | \\ &|0\rangle_{10}^1 \triangleright \square_{11}^{\frac{1}{2}} \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0 | |0\rangle_{20}^0 \triangleright \star_{21}^1 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1] \\ &= [2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{01}^0 \triangleright \diamond_{02}^{\frac{1}{3}} \triangleright \star_{03}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 | \\ i2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{01}^1 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0 | |0\rangle_{20}^0 \triangleright \star_{21}^1 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1] \\ &= [-2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{02}^0 \triangleright \star_{03}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 | i2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{01}^1 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0 | \\ \frac{1}{2} |0\rangle_{21}^0 \oplus i\frac{3^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2} |1\rangle_{21}^0 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1] \\ &= [-2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{03}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 | i2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{01}^1 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0 | \\ \frac{1}{2} |0\rangle_{21}^0 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1, i\frac{3^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2} |1\rangle_{21}^0 \triangleright \square_{11} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1] \\ &= [-2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{03}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 | \frac{1}{2} |0\rangle_{11}^1 \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1, \\ i2^{-\frac{1}{2}} |0\rangle_{11}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0, i\frac{3^{\frac{1}{2}}}{2} |1\rangle_{11}^0 \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0] \\ &= [\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}} \triangleright \triangle_{04}^0 | i\frac{1/2}{\sqrt{-2-\sqrt{6}}} \triangleright \triangle_{22}^1, i\frac{\sqrt{3}/2}{\sqrt{-2-\sqrt{6}}} \triangleright \triangle_{12}^0] \\ &= [(|\frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}|^2)_0 | (|i\frac{\sqrt{3}/2}{\sqrt{-2-\sqrt{6}/2}}|^2)_0, (|i\frac{1/2}{\sqrt{-2-\sqrt{6}/2}}|^2)_1] \\ &\simeq [(0.5)_0 | (0.91)_0, (0.09)_1] \end{aligned}$$

Again, we do not have space to explain the details of the rules applied in the equational deduction below. Observe, however, that there is a special approach to measurements. As we mentioned in the previous section, this kind of operation requires a formalization different from regular algebraic ones.

The deduction above exemplifies this point. Another feature is the transformation of nodes linked to others nodes in rows. In synalgebra, these transformations are regulated by rules, as indicated in the previous section, for flow of information.

IV. LEVELS OF ABSTRACTIONS AND CONCRETIONS

To illustrate the potential of the Kantian-Peircean perspective, we present preliminary data from a synalgebraic implementation of the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE).

The Fig. V below displays a synalgebraic representation of the basic *building block* of the VQE presented in [18]. The photonic circuits simulated are vertical concatenations of these building blocks. Hence, the number of qubits is the number of these blocks.

VQE building block (Fig. V)

We have been developing a synalgebraic library for photonic circuits in Rust, due to its safe concurrent model and its integration with hardware description languages to run on FPGAs. Below, we present preliminary data from computations of VQE. The simulations were conducted on a Dell desktop with an Intel Core i7-1355U CPU and 15 GiB of RAM. For these simulations, we ran triplicates of VQEs with 10 up to 100 qubits, but not for all possible inputs, just for $10t$ number of qubits, where $t = 1, \dots, 10$.

Fig. 2. Simulations on VQEs runs

These results indicate that increasing the number of qubits for VQEs leads to only linear computational complexity for writing the formulas and processing the computations. This behavior is due to the linear growth of nodes and links in proportion to the number of qubits. This *does not* mean that our framework provide *efficient exact simulations* of VQEs, instead it shows that they can be *efficiently approximated*.

Indeed, we do not claim any large-scale simulation result yet, because, for the sake of statistical analysis, we still need

to perform improvements in the library. We prefer instead to indicate that the synalgebraic framework sounds so powerful that we can, by its turn, to integrate the classical optimization algorithm of a VQE as well. Fig. VI illustrate that possibility:

VQE integrated with classical optimizer (Fig. VI)

In our work [8], we explore this possibility of abstraction of all components of a VQE algorithm in photonic circuits based on Hartree-Fock theory. Unlike previous works, in our approach the classical optimization stage of VQE, using the Nelder-Mead method, is also computationally integrated. This suggests the potential for fully automated analysis of VQE in quantum chemistry.

In the direction of implementations of concrete photonic quantum hardware, we would like to mention the possibility of minimizing bend loss (MBL) in waveguide channel routing. Sharma and Roy in [20] presented an approach to MBL based on the representation of waveguides as paths in grids. Fig. VII illustrates how MBL can be described in terms of intergraphs:

Synalgebraic minimization bend loss (Fig. VII)

In Fig. VII, the intergraph A is the waveguide to be optimized. There are two paths, *blue* and *red*, which are parameterized by points in the nodes of A . The paths in A are mapped into another intergraph B through an homomorphism $Optimize(blue, red)$ that makes the optimization of the paths according to some metrics. The intergraphs A and B have an isomorphic lattice structure underling it. This situation requires an extension of intergraphs with labeled links. As we have emphasized along this paper paper, synalgebra is quite flexible. Such an adaptation to MBL shows that synalgebra is not only one more possible abstraction. It is, indeed, an abstraction, but which also may have applications in concrete photonic quantum hardware.

In future work, we plan to present the full details of the synalgebraic framework and explore the possibilities indicated above. We are confident that if the reader is also excited with the *ethos* of the Kantian-Peircean perspective outlined here, they will also find many other possibilities. To keep the motivation high, we end with a famous Kant's quote from the *Critique of Practical Reason*: "Two things fill the mind with ever new and increasing wonder and awe, the starry heavens above and the moral law within."

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